

**HISTORY-DEPENDENT DIFFERENTIAL
VARIATIONAL-HEMIVARIATIONAL INEQUALITIES WITH
APPLICATIONS TO CONTACT MECHANICS**

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Dedicated to Professor Meir Shillor on the occasion of his 70th birthday.

ABSTRACT. The primary objective of this paper is to explore a complicated differential variational-hemivariational inequality involving a history-dependent operator in Banach spaces. A well-posedness result for the inequality, including the existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependence on the initial data of the solution is established by using a fixed point principle for history-dependent operators. Moreover, to illustrate the applicability of the theoretical results, an elastic contact problem with wear and long time dependent effort is explored.

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1. Introduction. Differential variational inequalities (DVI, for short) as the powerful mathematical tools, which were systematically introduced and investigated by Pang-Stewart [20] in finite-dimensional spaces, have been applied to the study of various problems involving both dynamics and constraints in the form of inequalities, which arise in many applied problems in our real life, for instance, mechanical impact problems, electrical circuits with ideal diodes, the Coulomb friction problems for contacting bodies, economical dynamics, dynamic traffic networks, and so on. Over the past decade, the theory and applications of DVIs grew rapidly. Comprehensive references in the area include: Liu et al. [8, 9, 10, 11] employed the theory of semigroups, Filippov implicit function lemma and fixed point theorems for condensing multivalued operators to establish the existence of mild solutions for a class of differential mixed variational inequalities in Banach spaces; Migórski-Zeng [16] introduced a temporally semi-discrete algorithm based on the backward Euler difference scheme together with a feedback iterative method to explore a differential hemivariational inequality, which is formulated by a parabolic hemivariational inequality and a nonlinear evolution equation in the framework of an evolution triple of spaces; by adopting the idea of DVIs, Chen-Wang [1] in 2014 discussed a dynamic Nash equilibrium problem of multiple players with shared constraints and dynamic decision processes; Zeng-Liu-Migórski [26] applied Rothe method combined with surjectivity of multivalued pseudomonotone operators to deliver an existence theorem to a class of fractional differential hemivariational inequalities in Banach spaces, and then utilized the theoretical results to study a frictional quasistatic contact problem for viscoelastic materials with adhesion; Gwinner [5] in 2013 established a stability result of a class of differential variational inequalities by using the monotonicity method and technique of the Mosco convergence. For more details on these topics the reader is welcome to consult [2, 7, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, 19, 25] and the references therein.

Everywhere in this paper, symbol I will denote either a bounded interval of the form $[0, T]$ with $T > 0$, or the unbounded interval $\mathbb{R}_+ := [0, +\infty)$. Let X, V be reflexive Banach spaces, Y be a normed space, and K be a nonempty, closed and convex subset of V . Given functions $F: I \times X \times V \rightarrow X$, $G: I \times X \times K \rightarrow V^*$, $\varphi: X \times Y \times K \times K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{R}: C(I; V) \times C(I; Y)$ and $j: X \times Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, in the current research, we are interesting in the study of the following generalized differential variational-hemivariational inequality involving history-dependent operator

Problem 1. Find functions $x: I \rightarrow X$ and $u: I \rightarrow V$ such that

$$\begin{cases} x'(t) = F(t, x(t), u(t)) & \text{for a.e. } t \in I, \\ x(0) = x_0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

and for all $t \in I$, $u(t) \in K$ satisfies the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, x(t), u(t)), v - u(t) \rangle + \varphi(x(t), (\mathcal{R}u)(t), u(t), v) - \varphi(x(t), (\mathcal{R}u)(t), u(t), u(t)) \\ & + j^0(x(t), u(t); v - u(t)) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } v \in K. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The aim of the paper is twofold. The first goal is to explore a well-posedness result for Problem 1, including the existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependence on the initial data of the solution. However, the second intention is to employ the abstract results to the study of a complicated elastic contact problem with wear in which a generalized elastic constitutive law with long memory effect is considered, and the wear is described by a nonlinear ordinary differential equation.

The outline of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we recall some preliminary materials, which will be needed in the sequel. Section 3 is devoted to explore a well-posedness result to Problem 1 by using the fixed point principle for history-dependent operators. In Section 4, an application of the abstract results, established in Section 3, to a complicated history-dependent elastic contact problem with wear is discussed.

2. Preliminaries. In the section, we recall some important notation, definitions and preliminary materials, which will be needed in the sequel. For more details, we refer to [3, 4, 15].

Let X be a reflexive Banach space with its dual space X^* and $h: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a locally Lipschitz function. The (Clarke) generalized directional derivative of h at $u \in X$ in the direction $v \in X$ is defined by

$$h^0(u; v) = \limsup_{y \rightarrow u, \lambda \downarrow 0} \frac{h(y + \lambda v) - h(y)}{\lambda}.$$

In the meantime, the Clarke subdifferential operator $\partial h: X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ of h is given by

$$\partial h(u) = \{ \zeta \in X^* \mid h^0(u; v) \geq \langle \zeta, v \rangle_{X^* \times X} \text{ for all } v \in X \} \quad \text{for all } u \in X.$$

The generalized gradient and generalized directional derivative of a locally Lipschitz function enjoy many nice properties and rich calculus. Here we just collect below some basic and crucial results, see for instance, [15, Proposition 3.23].

Proposition 1. *Let $h: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a locally Lipschitz function, then the following statements are true*

- (i) *for each $x \in X$, $\partial h(x)$ is nonempty, convex and weakly compact in X^* .*
- (ii) *the graph of ∂h is closed in $X \times (w^* - X^*)$ topology, i.e., if $\{x_n\} \subset X$ and $\{\xi_n\} \subset X^*$ are such that $\xi_n \in \partial h(x_n)$ and $x_n \rightarrow x$ in X , $\xi_n \rightarrow \xi$ weakly* in X^* , then it holds $\xi \in \partial h(x)$.*
- (iii) *the multivalued mapping $X \ni x \rightarrow \partial h(x) \subseteq X^*$ is upper semicontinuous from X into $w^* - X^*$.*

Next, we recall the following fixed point principle for history-dependent operators, see cf. [23].

Lemma 2.1. *Let X be a Banach space and $\mathcal{S}: C(I; X) \rightarrow C(I; X)$ be a history-dependent operator, namely, for each compact set $J \subset I$, there exists $M_J > 0$ satisfying*

$$\|\mathcal{S}x_1(t) - \mathcal{S}x_2(t)\|_X \leq M_J \int_0^t \|x_1(s) - x_2(s)\|_X ds$$

for all $t \in J$, and all $x_1, x_2 \in C(I; X)$. Then, \mathcal{S} has a unique fixed point in $C(I; X)$, i.e., there exists a unique function $u \in C(I; X)$ such that $u = \mathcal{S}u$.

Given a function $u \in C(I; V)$, we recall the following uniqueness and existence result for Cauchy problem (1).

Lemma 2.2. *Let X and V be Banach spaces and the following conditions hold: $\underline{H}(F): F: I \times X \times V \rightarrow X$ is such that*

- (i) *for all $x \in X$ and $u \in V$, the function $t \mapsto F(t, x, u): I \rightarrow X$ is continuous.*

(ii) for each compact set $J \subset I$, there exists a constant $L_J > 0$ satisfying

$$\|F(t, x, u) - F(t, y, v)\|_X \leq L_J(\|x - y\|_X + \|u - v\|_V)$$

for all $x, y \in X$, $u, v \in V$ and $t \in J$.

Then, for each function $u \in C(I; V)$ and $x_0 \in X$, there exists a unique solution $x \in C(I; X)$ to solve Cauchy problem (1). Moreover, given $u_1, u_2 \in C(I; V)$, if $x_1, x_2 \in C(I; X)$ are the unique solutions to Cauchy problem (1) corresponding to u_1 and u_2 , accordingly, then for each compact set $J \subset I$, we have

$$\|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \leq L_J^* e^{L_J^* t} \int_0^t \|u_1(s) - u_2(s)\|_V ds \quad (3)$$

for all $t \in J$ for some $L_J^* > 0$.

In the end of the section, we shall introduce the usual notation and symbols, which will be used in the study of the elastic contact problem in Section 4.

Let Ω be a bounded and connected domain in \mathbb{R}^d , where $(d = 2, 3)$, such that the boundary $\Gamma = \partial\Omega$ is Lipschitz continuous. The normal and tangential components of a vector field $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$ on the boundary are given by

$$\xi_\nu = \xi \cdot \nu \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_\tau = \xi - \xi_\nu \nu,$$

where $\nu = (\nu_i)$ denotes the outward unit normal at the boundary. Also, \mathbb{S}^d denotes the space of real symmetric $d \times d$ matrices. However, the notation σ_ν and σ_τ represents the normal and tangential components of the stress field $\sigma \in \mathbb{S}^d$ on the boundary, that is, $\sigma_\nu = (\sigma \nu) \cdot \nu$ and $\sigma_\tau = \sigma \nu - \sigma_\nu \nu$. On \mathbb{R}^d and \mathbb{S}^d we use the standard notation for inner products and norms defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \xi \cdot \eta &= \xi_i \eta_i, \quad \|\xi\| = (\xi \cdot \xi)^{1/2} \quad \text{for} \quad \xi = (\xi_i), \quad \eta = (\eta_i) \in \mathbb{R}^d, \\ \sigma : \tau &= \sigma_{ij} \tau_{ij}, \quad \|\sigma\| = (\sigma : \sigma)^{1/2} \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma = (\sigma_{ij}), \quad \tau = (\tau_{ij}) \in \mathbb{S}^d. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $i, j, k, l \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and the summation convention over repeated indices is used. In addition, we use the notation $\mathbf{u} = (u_i)$, $\sigma = (\sigma_{ij})$, and

$$\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}) = (\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{u})), \quad \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}), \quad i, j = 1, \dots, d,$$

to denote the displacement vector, the stress tensor, and the linearized strain tensor, respectively.

3. Well-posedness result. This section is devoted to explore a well-posedness result for a comprehensive differential variational-hemivariational inequality, Problem 1, including the existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependence on the initial data of the solution.

Under the framework mentioned in Section 1, we impose the following assumptions.

$H(K)$: K is a nonempty, closed and convex subset of V .

$H(G)$: $G: I \times X \times K \rightarrow V^*$ is such that

(i) for every $t \in I$ and $x \in X$, the function $u \mapsto G(t, x, u)$ is strongly monotone, i.e., there is a constant $m_G > 0$ such that

$$\langle G(t, x, u) - G(t, x, v), u - v \rangle \geq m_G \|u - v\|_V^2$$

for all $u, v \in K$.

(ii) there exists a constant $L_G > 0$ such that

$$\|G(t_1, x_1, u) - G(t_2, x_2, u)\|_{V^*} \leq L_G(|t_1 - t_2| + \|x_1 - x_2\|_X)$$

for all $t_1, t_2 \in I$, $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and $u \in K$.

$H(\mathcal{R})$: $\mathcal{R}: C(I; V) \rightarrow C(I; Y)$ is a history-dependent operator, namely, for each compact set $J_0 \subset I$, there is a constant $L_0 > 0$ such that

$$\|(\mathcal{R}u)(t) - (\mathcal{R}v)(t)\|_Y \leq L_0 \int_0^t \|u(s) - v(s)\|_V ds$$

for all $u, v \in C(I; V)$ and all $t \in J_0$.

$H(j)$: $j: X \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is such that

- (i) for each $x \in X$, the function $u \mapsto j(x, u): V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is locally Lipschitz.
- (ii) there is a constant $c_j \geq 0$ such that

$$\|\partial j(x, u)\|_{V^*} \leq c_j(1 + \|x\|_X + \|u\|_V)$$

for all $x \in X$ and $u \in V$.

- (iii) there exist $\alpha_j \geq 0$ and $\beta_j \geq 0$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} & j^0(x_1, u_1; u_2 - u_1) + j^0(x_2, u_2; u_1 - u_2) \\ & \leq \alpha_j \|u_1 - u_2\|_V^2 + \beta_j \|u_1 - u_2\|_V \|x_1 - x_2\|_X \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and $u_1, u_2 \in V$.

$H(\varphi)$: $\varphi: X \times Y \times K \times K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is such that

- (i) for all $x \in X$, $y \in Y$ and $v \in K$, the function $u \mapsto \varphi(x, y, v, u): K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is convex and l.s.c. on K .
- (ii) there exist $\alpha_\varphi \geq 0$, $\beta_\varphi \geq 0$, and $\gamma_\varphi \geq 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi(x_1, y_1, u_1, v_2) - \varphi(x_1, y_1, u_1, v_1) + \varphi(x_2, y_2, u_2, v_1) - \varphi(x_2, y_2, u_2, v_2) \\ & \leq \alpha_\varphi \|u_1 - u_2\|_V \|v_1 - v_2\|_V + \beta_\varphi \|y_1 - y_2\|_Y \|v_1 - v_2\|_V \\ & \quad + \gamma_\varphi \|x_1 - x_2\|_X \|v_1 - v_2\|_V \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_1, x_2 \in X$, $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ and $u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2 \in K$.

$H(0)$: $\alpha_\varphi + \alpha_j < m_G$.

We now provide the main results of the section as follows.

Theorem 3.1. *Assume that $H(K)$, $H(F)$, $H(G)$, $H(\varphi)$, $H(j)$, $H(\mathcal{R})$ and $H(0)$ are satisfied. Then, for each $x_0 \in X$, Problem 1 has a unique solution $(x, u) \in C(I; X) \times C(I; V)$. Moreover, for $x_0, y_0 \in X$ fixed, for each compact set $J \subset I$, there exists a constant $M_J > 0$ such that*

$$\|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X + \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V \leq M_J \|x_0 - y_0\|_X \quad (4)$$

for all $t \in J$, where (x_1, u_1) and (x_2, u_2) are the unique solutions to Problem 1 corresponding to x_0 and y_0 , respectively.

Proof. For any $x \in C(I; X)$ fixed, it follows from [22, Theorem 93, p.160] that history-dependent variational-hemivariational inequality (2) admits a unique solution $u_x \in C(I; V)$. Consider the mapping $P: C(I; X) \rightarrow C(I; V)$ by

$$Px = u_x \quad \text{for all } x \in C(I; X), \quad (5)$$

where $u_x \in C(I; V)$ is the unique solution to problem (2) corresponding to $x \in C(I; X)$.

Let $x_i \in C(I; X)$ and $u_i = Px_i$ for $i = 1, 2$, hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, x_1(t), u_1(t)), v - u_1(t) \rangle + \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), v) \\ & - \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), u_1(t)) + j^0(x_1(t), u_1(t); v - u_1(t)) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, x_2(t), u_2(t)), v - u_2(t) \rangle + \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), v) \\ & - \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), u_2(t)) + j^0(x_2(t), u_2(t); v - u_2(t)) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

for all $v \in K$ and all $t \in I$. Inserting $v = u_2(t)$ and $v = u_1(t)$ into (6) and (7), respectively, we sum the resulting inequalities to yield

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, x_1(t), u_1(t)) - G(t, x_1(t), u_2(t)), u_1(t) - u_2(t) \rangle \\ & \leq \langle G(t, x_2(t), u_2(t)) - G(t, x_1(t), u_2(t)), u_1(t) - u_2(t) \rangle \\ & + \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), u_2(t)) - \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), u_1(t)) \\ & + \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), u_1(t)) - \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), u_2(t)) \\ & + j^0(x_1(t), u_1(t); u_2(t) - u_1(t)) + j^0(x_2(t), u_2(t); u_1(t) - u_2(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

for all $t \in I$. The strong monotonicity of $u \mapsto G(t, x, u)$ and Lipschitz continuity of $x \mapsto G(t, x, u)$ imply

$$m_G \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V^2 \leq \langle G(t, x_1(t), u_1(t)) - G(t, x_1(t), u_2(t)), u_1(t) - u_2(t) \rangle \quad (9)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, x_2(t), u_2(t)) - G(t, x_1(t), u_2(t)), u_1(t) - u_2(t) \rangle \\ & \leq L_G \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Besides, conditions $H(\varphi)$ (ii) and $H(j)$ (iii) reveal

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), u_2(t)) - \varphi(x_1(t), (\mathcal{R}u_1)(t), u_1(t), u_1(t)) \\ & + \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), u_1(t)) - \varphi(x_2(t), (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t), u_2(t), u_2(t)) \\ & \leq \alpha_\varphi \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V^2 + \beta_\varphi \|(\mathcal{R}u_1)(t) - (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t)\|_Y \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V \\ & + \gamma_\varphi \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & j^0(x_1(t), u_1(t); u_2(t) - u_1(t)) + j^0(x_2(t), u_2(t); u_1(t) - u_2(t)) \\ & \leq \alpha_j \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V^2 + \beta_j \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Recall that \mathcal{R} is a history-dependent operator, for each compact set $J \subset I$, it finds

$$\|(\mathcal{R}u_1)(t) - (\mathcal{R}u_2)(t)\|_Y \leq L_J \int_0^t \|u_1(s) - u_2(s)\|_V ds \quad \text{for all } t \in J, \quad (13)$$

with some $L_J > 0$. Taking account of (8)–(13), and the smallness condition $H(0)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V \\ & \leq \frac{(L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi)}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X + \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \int_0^t \|u_1(s) - u_2(s)\|_V ds \end{aligned}$$

for all $t \in I$. Invoking Gronwall inequality deduces

$$\begin{aligned} & \|Px_1(t) - Px_2(t)\|_V = \|u_1(t) - u_2(t)\|_V \\ & \leq \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J (L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi) e^{\frac{\beta_\varphi L_J t}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)}}}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)^2} \int_0^t \|x_1(s) - x_2(s)\|_X ds \\ & \quad + \frac{(L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi)}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

for all $t \in I$.

On the other hand, it follows from Lemma 2.2 and hypotheses $H(F)$ that for each $u \in C(I; V)$ fixed, there exists a unique function $x \in C(I; X)$ to solve the Cauchy problem (1) and the identity holds

$$x(t) = x_0 + \int_0^t F(s, x(s), u(s)) ds \quad \text{for all } t \in I.$$

Let $u_1, u_2 \in C(I; V)$ be arbitrary, and $x_1, x_2 \in C(I; X)$ be the unique solutions of Cauchy problem (1) associated to u_1 and u_2 , respectively. Employing Lemma 2.2 again, it concludes that for each compact set $J \subset I$, we are able to find $L_J^* > 0$ such that (3) holds for all $t \in J$. Further, consider the function $Q: C(I; V) \rightarrow C(I; X)$ defined by

$$Qu = x_u \quad \text{for all } u \in C(I; V), \quad (15)$$

where x_u is the unique solution to Cauchy problem (1) corresponding to $u \in C(I; V)$.

It is not difficult to see that $x \in C(I; X)$ is a fixed point of $Q \circ P: C(I; X) \rightarrow C(I; X)$ if and only if $(x, Px) \in C(I; X) \times C(I; V)$ is a solution to Problem 1. Taking advantage of the fact, next, we shall illustrate that $Q \circ P: C(I; X) \rightarrow C(I; X)$ has a unique fixed point in $C(I; X)$. Let $x_1, x_2 \in C(I; X)$ be arbitrary. From (14) and (3), it yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \|Q(Px_1)(t) - Q(Px_2)(t)\|_X \leq L_J^* e^{L_J^* t} \int_0^t \|Px_1(s) - Px_2(s)\|_V ds \\ & \leq \frac{(L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi) L_J^* e^{L_J^* t}}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \int_0^t \|x_1(s) - x_2(s)\|_X ds \\ & \quad + L_J^* e^{L_J^* t} \int_0^t \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J (L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi) e^{\frac{\beta_\varphi L_J s}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)}}}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)^2} \int_0^s \|x_1(\tau) - x_2(\tau)\|_X d\tau ds \\ & \leq R_J \left(L_J^* e^{L_J^* t} + L_J^* e^{\left(L_J^* + \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \right) t} \right) \int_0^t \|x_1(s) - x_2(s)\|_X ds \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

for all $t \in J$, where $R_J > 0$ is defined by

$$R_J := \frac{(L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi)}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} + \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J (L_G + \beta_j + \gamma_\varphi)}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)^2}.$$

Exploring Lemma 2.1 and (16), we conclude that $Q \circ P: C(I; X) \rightarrow C(I; X)$ has a unique fixed point, say, $x \in C(I; X)$. Therefore, Problem 1 has a unique solution $(x, Px) \in C(I; X) \times C(I; V)$.

Let $x_0, y_0 \in X$ be fixed. Assume that $(x_1, u_1), (x_2, u_2) \in C(I; X) \times C(I; V)$ are the unique solutions to Problem 1 corresponding to x_0 and y_0 , respectively. Therefore, for each compact set $J \subset I$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \\ & \leq \|x_0 - y_0\|_X + L_J \int_0^t (\|x_1(s) - x_2(s)\|_X + \|u_1(s) - u_2(s)\|_V) ds \end{aligned}$$

for all $t \in J$ with some $L_J > 0$, where we have used the condition $H(F)$ (ii). The latter together with the Gronwall inequality deduces

$$\|x_1(t) - x_2(t)\|_X \leq \left(\|x_0 - y_0\|_X + L_J \int_0^t \|u_1(s) - u_2(s)\|_V ds \right) e^{L_J t} \quad (17)$$

for all $t \in J$. Combining (14) and (17) with Gronwall inequality, we can find $M_J > 0$ such that (4) holds. \square

4. A history-dependent elastic contact problem with wear. To illustrate the applicability of the theoretical results obtained in Section 3, the current section is concerned with the study of an impressive application to Contact Mechanics. More precisely, an elastic contact problem with wear and long time dependent effort is explored. In what follows, the time interval of interest is I , which could be either a bounded interval of the form $[0, T]$ for some $T > 0$, or the unbounded interval $\mathbb{R}_+ = [0, +\infty)$. Additionally, in order to simplify the notation, we do not indicate explicitly the dependence of various functions on the spatial variable \mathbf{x} .

The physical setting of the contact problem is given as follows. An elastic body occupies a bounded domain Ω in \mathbb{R}^d for $d = 2, 3$ with a Lipschitz continuous boundary Γ , which is considered to be divided into four measurable parts $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \Gamma_3$ and Γ_4 such that $meas(\Gamma_1) > 0$, where Γ_3 is particularly assumed to be a plane. Also let \mathbf{v}^* be the velocity of the foundation. Besides, we set $\mathcal{Q} = \Omega \times I$, $\Sigma = \Gamma \times I$, $\Sigma_1 = \Gamma_1 \times I$, $\Sigma_2 = \Gamma_2 \times I$, $\Sigma_3 = \Gamma_3 \times I$ and $\Sigma_4 = \Gamma_4 \times I$.

We now provide the classical formulation of the contact problem as follows.

Problem 2. Find a displacement field $\mathbf{u}: \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, a stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}: \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d$, and a wear function $w: \Sigma_3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = \mathcal{A}(t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(t))) + \int_0^t \mathcal{B}(t-s, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(s))) ds \quad \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Div } \boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) + \mathbf{f}_0(t) = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{on } \Sigma_1, \quad (20)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t)\boldsymbol{\nu} = \mathbf{f}_2(t) \quad \text{on } \Sigma_2, \quad (21)$$

$$-\sigma_\nu(t) = p_\nu(u_\nu(t) - w(t)) \quad \text{on } \Sigma_3, \quad (22)$$

$$-\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\tau(t) = \eta|\sigma_\nu(t)|\mathbf{n}^*(t) \quad \text{on} \quad \Sigma_3, \quad (23)$$

$$w'(t) = h(t, u_\nu(t), w(t)) \quad \text{on} \quad \Sigma_3, \quad (24)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \quad \text{on} \quad \Gamma_3, \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{cases} u_\nu(t) \leq g \\ \sigma_\nu(t) + \xi_\nu(t) \leq 0 \\ (u_\nu(t) - g)(\sigma_\nu(t) + \xi_\nu(t)) = 0 \\ \xi_\nu(t) \in \partial j_\nu(u_\nu(t)) \end{cases} \quad \text{on} \quad \Sigma_4, \quad (26)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\tau(t) = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{on} \quad \Sigma_4. \quad (27)$$

We now provide a brief description on the equations, conditions and relations appeared in Problem 2. Equation (18) is a generalized elastic constitutive law with long memory effect (see e.g. [15, Section 6, p. 182]), where $\mathcal{A}: \mathcal{Q} \times \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d$ is a nonlinear elasticity operator, and $\mathcal{B}: \mathcal{Q} \times \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d$ is a relaxation operator in which both operators \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} depend on the location of the point $t \in I$. Additionally, we assume that the elasticity operator \mathcal{A} and relaxation function \mathcal{B} in the constitutive law (18) satisfy the following conditions.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{A}: \mathcal{Q} \times \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d \text{ is such that} \\ (a) \mathcal{A}(\cdot, \cdot, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \text{ is measurable on } \mathcal{Q}, \text{ for all } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \in \mathbb{S}^d. \\ (b) \text{ there exists } L_{\mathcal{A}} > 0 \text{ such that} \\ \quad \|\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, t_1, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1) - \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, t_2, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2)\|_{\mathbb{S}^d} \leq L_{\mathcal{A}}(|t_1 - t_2| + \|\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2\|_{\mathbb{S}^d}) \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, \text{ all } t_1, t_2 \in I \text{ and all } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \in \mathbb{S}^d. \\ (c) \text{ there exists } \alpha_{\mathcal{A}} > 0 \text{ such that} \\ \quad (\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1) - \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2)) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2) \geq \alpha_{\mathcal{A}}\|\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2\|_{\mathbb{S}^d}^2 \\ \quad \text{for all } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \in \mathbb{S}^d \text{ and a.e. } (\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathcal{Q}. \\ (d) \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{x}, t, \mathbf{0}_{\mathbb{S}^d}) = \mathbf{0}_{\mathbb{S}^d} \text{ for a.e. } (\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathcal{Q}. \end{array} \right. \quad (28)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{B}: \mathcal{Q} \times \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d \text{ is such that for each compact set } J \subset I, \\ \text{there exists a constant } \mathcal{L}_J > 0 \text{ such that} \\ \quad \|\mathcal{B}(\mathbf{x}, t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1) - \mathcal{B}(\mathbf{x}, t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2)\|_{\mathbb{S}^d} \leq \mathcal{L}_J\|\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2\|_{\mathbb{S}^d} \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, \text{ all } t \in J \text{ and all } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \in \mathbb{S}^d. \end{array} \right. \quad (29)$$

However, (19) is the equation of equilibrium, and we use it since we assume that the inertial term in the equation motion is neglected. Here, Div stands for the divergence operator, i.e.,

$$\text{Div}\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_{ij,j}).$$

The boundary conditions (20) and (21) characterize the physical phenomena that the elastic body is clamped on Γ_1 and it is subjected to the density $\mathbf{f}_2(t)$ of surface tractions on Γ_2 at time $t \in I$. The boundary condition (22) represents a normal contact condition with wear effect on boundary Γ_3 (see for example, [6, 21]) in which

the normal compliance function p reads the following conditions.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p: \Gamma_3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+ \text{ is such that} \\ (a) \text{ for all } r \in \mathbb{R}, \text{ the function } \mathbf{x} \mapsto p(\mathbf{x}, r) \text{ is measurable on } \Gamma_3. \\ (b) \text{ there exists a constant } L_p > 0 \text{ satisfying} \\ \quad |p(\mathbf{x}, r_1) - p(\mathbf{x}, r_2)| \leq L_p |r_1 - r_2| \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_3 \text{ and all } r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{R}. \\ (c) \text{ for all } r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_3, \text{ we have} \\ \quad (p(\mathbf{x}, r_1) - p(\mathbf{x}, r_2))(r_1 - r_2) \geq 0. \\ (d) p(\mathbf{x}, r) = 0 \text{ for all } r \leq 0 \text{ and a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_3. \end{array} \right. \quad (30)$$

For the velocity of the foundation \mathbf{v}^* , we suppose that it is a non-vanishing time-dependent function (i.e., $\mathbf{v}^*(t) \neq \mathbf{0}_{\mathbb{R}^d}$ for all $t \in I$) in the plane of Γ_3 and reads the condition

$$\mathbf{v}^* \in C(I; \mathbb{R}^d). \quad (31)$$

However, under the assumption that the velocity of the foundation \mathbf{v}^* is large in comparison with the tangential velocity of the elastic body, we have the equation (23), which stands for the sliding version of the classical Coulomb law of dry friction (see [24], for more details), where \mathbf{n}^* is the unitary vector given by

$$\mathbf{n}^*(t) = -\frac{\mathbf{v}^*(t)}{\|\mathbf{v}^*(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}} \quad \text{for all } t \in I.$$

Besides, in the equation (23), the coefficient η is assumed to enjoy the following regularity

$$\eta \in L^\infty(\Gamma_3) \quad \text{with} \quad \eta(\mathbf{x}) > 0 \text{ for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_3. \quad (32)$$

On the other side, the wear function w is considered to be governed by a nonlinear ordinary differential equation (29) depending on the normal displacement $u_\nu(t)$, and formulated on contact surface Γ_3 , where the function $h: \Sigma_3 \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the following conditions.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h: \Sigma_3 \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ is such that} \\ (a) \text{ for all } r, s \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and } t \in I, \text{ the function } \mathbf{x} \mapsto h(\mathbf{x}, t, r, s) \\ \quad \text{is measurable on } \Gamma_3. \\ (b) \text{ for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_3 \text{ and all } r, s \in \mathbb{R}, \text{ the function } t \mapsto h(\mathbf{x}, t, r, s) \\ \quad \text{is continuous on } I. \\ (c) \text{ for each compact set } J \subset I, \text{ there exists a constant } L_J > 0 \text{ satisfying} \\ \quad |h(\mathbf{x}, t, r_1, s_1) - h(\mathbf{x}, t, r_2, s_2)| \leq L_J (|r_1 - r_2| + |s_1 - s_2|) \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } (\mathbf{x}, t) \in \Sigma_3 \text{ and all } r_1, r_2, s_1, s_2 \in \mathbb{R}. \end{array} \right. \quad (33)$$

Particularly, if h is specialized to be the formulation

$$h(t, u_\nu(t), w(t)) = k \|\mathbf{v}^*(t)\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} p(u_\nu(t) - w(t)) \quad \text{for all } (\mathbf{x}, t) \in \Sigma_3,$$

then equation (24) reduces the classical version of the Archard's law for wear function w . However, condition (25) represents the initial condition for the wear function. In fact, if we take $w_0 = 0$, then we can see that at the initial moment the material is new.

Whereas, boundary condition (26) models the contact with a foundation made of a rigid body covered by a deformable layer of thickness g on Γ_4 , where g is assumed to be a positive constant. In the meanwhile, we assume that j_ν is a locally Lipschitz function (or superpotential) to satisfy the following conditions

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} j_\nu : \Gamma_4 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ is such that} \\ (a) \text{ for all } r \in \mathbb{R}, \text{ the function } \mathbf{x} \mapsto j_\nu(\mathbf{x}, r) \text{ is measurable on } \Gamma_4, \\ \text{and there exists } e \in L^2(\Gamma_4) \text{ such that } j_\nu(\cdot, e(\cdot)) \in L^1(\Gamma_4). \\ (b) \text{ for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_4, r \mapsto j_\nu(\mathbf{x}, r) \text{ is locally Lipschitz on } \mathbb{R}. \\ (c) \text{ there exist } c_0 \geq 0 \text{ and } c_1 > 0 \text{ such that} \\ \quad |\partial j_\nu(\mathbf{x}, r)| \leq c_0 + c_1 |r| \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_4 \text{ and all } r \in \mathbb{R}. \\ (d) \text{ there is } \alpha_{j_\nu} \geq 0 \text{ such that} \\ \quad j_\nu^0(\mathbf{x}, r_1; r_2 - r_1) + j_\nu^0(\mathbf{x}, r_2; r_1 - r_2) \leq \alpha_{j_\nu} |r_1 - r_2|^2 \\ \quad \text{for a.e. } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_4 \text{ and all } r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{R}. \end{array} \right. \quad (34)$$

Here, ∂j_ν denotes the Clarke subdifferential of j_ν with respect to the last variable.

Finally, condition (27) represents the frictionless contact condition on Γ_4 .

To obtain the variational formulation of Problem 2, we consider the following function spaces:

$$V := \{ \mathbf{v} \in H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d) \mid \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0} \text{ on } \Gamma_1 \},$$

$$Q := \{ \tau = (\tau_{ij}) \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{S}^d) \mid \tau_{ij} = \tau_{ji} \text{ for all } i, j = 1, \dots, d \}.$$

It is not difficult to prove that V and Q are both Hilbert spaces endowed with the inner products

$$\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_V := \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}) \, d\mathbf{x}, \quad (\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\tau})_Q := \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\tau} \, d\mathbf{x}$$

for all $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$, and all $\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\tau} \in Q$, respectively. Also, the associated norms on spaces V and Q are denoted by $\|\cdot\|_V$ and $\|\cdot\|_Q$, respectively. Moreover, we introduce the set of admissible displacement fields K by

$$K := \{ \mathbf{v} \in V \mid v_\nu \leq g \text{ on } \Gamma_4 \}. \quad (35)$$

From the Sobolev trace theorem, we are able to find the smallest constant $r_0 > 0$ (which only relies on Ω , Γ_1 and Γ_4) such that

$$\|\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2(\Gamma_4)} \leq r_0 \|\mathbf{v}\|_V \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in V.$$

Recall that the Green's formula

$$\int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}) \, d\mathbf{x} + \int_{\Omega} \text{Div} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, d\mathbf{x} = \int_{\Gamma} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \boldsymbol{\nu} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, d\Gamma \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in V,$$

it is not difficult to use this formula to obtain the variational formulation of Problem 2 as follows.

Problem 3. Find a wear function $w : I \rightarrow L^2(\Gamma_3)$ and a displacement field $\mathbf{u} : I \rightarrow K$ such that

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} w'(t) = h(t, u_\nu(t), w(t)) \quad \text{for a.e. } t \in I \\ w(0) = w_0, \end{array} \right. \quad (36)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbf{u}(t) \in K, \quad (\mathcal{A}(t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(t))) + \int_0^t \mathcal{B}(t-s, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(s))) ds, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(t)))_Q \\
& + \int_{\Gamma_3} p(u_\nu(t) - w(t))(v_\nu - u_\nu(t)) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} \eta p(u_\nu(t) - w(t)) \mathbf{n}^*(t) (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau(t)) d\Gamma \\
& + \int_{\Gamma_4} j_\nu^0(u_\nu(t); v_\nu - u_\nu(t)) d\Gamma \geq \langle \mathbf{f}(t), \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(t) \rangle_V
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

for all $\mathbf{v} \in K$ and all $t \in I$, where for each $t \in I$, $\mathbf{f}(t) \in V^*$ is such that

$$\langle \mathbf{f}(t), \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = \int_\Omega \mathbf{f}_0(t) \cdot \mathbf{v} d\mathbf{x} + \int_{\Gamma_2} \mathbf{f}_2(t) \cdot \mathbf{v} d\Gamma \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in V.$$

Theorem 4.1. Assume that (28)–(34) hold. If $\alpha_A > L_p \|\eta\|_{L^\infty(\Gamma_3)} + \alpha_{j_\nu} r_0^2$, then, Problem 3 has a unique solution $(\mathbf{u}, w) \in C(I; K) \times C(I; L^2(\Gamma_3))$.

Proof. Let $X = L^2(\Gamma_3)$, $Y = V^*$, and consider the functions $G: I \times X \times V \rightarrow V^*$, $\mathcal{R}: C(I; V) \rightarrow C(I; V^*)$ and $\varphi: X \times Y \times V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$\langle G(t, w, \mathbf{u}), \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = (\mathcal{A}(t, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}(t))), \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}))_Q + \int_{\Gamma_3} p(u_\nu - w) v_\nu d\Gamma - \langle \mathbf{f}(t), \mathbf{v} \rangle_V \tag{38}$$

$$\langle (\mathcal{R}\mathbf{z})(t), \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = \left(\int_0^t \mathcal{B}(t-s, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{z}(s))) ds, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}) \right)_Q \tag{39}$$

$$\varphi(w, \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \langle \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{v} \rangle_V + \int_{\Gamma_3} \eta p(u_\nu - w) \mathbf{n}^*(t) \cdot \mathbf{v}_\tau d\Gamma \tag{40}$$

for all $t \in I$, $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$, $\mathbf{v}^* \in V^*$, $w \in X$, and all $\mathbf{z} \in C(I; V)$. Also, we introduce functions $F: I \times X \times V \rightarrow X$ and $j: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$F(t, w, \mathbf{u}) := h(t, u_\nu, w), \tag{41}$$

$$j(\mathbf{u}) := \int_{\Gamma_4} j_\nu(\mathbf{x}, u_\nu(\mathbf{x})) d\Gamma. \tag{42}$$

for all $t \in I$, $w \in X$, and all $\mathbf{u} \in V$.

Consider the following intermediate problem: find functions $\mathbf{u}: I \rightarrow K$ and $w: I \rightarrow X$ such that

$$\begin{cases} w'(t) = F(t, w(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) & \text{for a.e. } t \in I, \\ w(0) = w_0, \end{cases} \tag{43}$$

and for all $t \in I$, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in K$ is a solution to the inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
& \langle G(t, w(t), \mathbf{u}(t)), \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(t) \rangle_V + j^0(\mathbf{u}(t); \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(t)) + \varphi(w(t), (\mathcal{R}\mathbf{u})(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \mathbf{v}) \\
& - \varphi(w(t), (\mathcal{R}\mathbf{u})(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in K.
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Invoking hypotheses (34) and [15, Theorem 3.47], we conclude that $j: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is locally Lipschitz continuous (i.e., $H(j)(i)$ is valid) and satisfies

$$j^0(\mathbf{u}; \mathbf{v}) \leq \int_{\Gamma_4} j_\nu^0(\mathbf{x}, u_\nu(\mathbf{x}); v_\nu(\mathbf{x})) d\Gamma, \tag{45}$$

$$\partial j(\mathbf{u}) \subset \int_{\Gamma_4} \partial j_\nu(\mathbf{x}, u_\nu(\mathbf{x})) d\Gamma \tag{46}$$

for all $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$. Hence, it is obvious that if $(\mathbf{u}, w) \in C(I; K) \times C(I; X)$ is a solution to problem (43)–(44), then it is also a solution to Problem 3. Based on this fact, we will utilize Theorem 3.1 to show that Problem 3 is solvable.

To end this, first, we assert that G , φ and \mathcal{R} read the conditions $H(G)$, $H(\varphi)$ and $H(\mathcal{R})$, respectively.

For any $t \in I$, $w \in X$, conditions (28)(c) and (30)(c) deduce

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle G(t, w, \mathbf{v}) - G(t, w, \mathbf{u}), \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle_V \\ &= (\mathcal{A}(t, \varepsilon(\mathbf{v})) - \mathcal{A}(t, \varepsilon(\mathbf{u})), \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}) - \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}))_Q \\ & \quad + \int_{\Gamma_3} (p(v_\nu - w) - p(u_\nu - w))(v_\nu - u_\nu) d\Gamma \\ & \geq \alpha_{\mathcal{A}} \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}\|_V^2 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in K$, so, $H(G)$ (i) holds with $m_G := \alpha_{\mathcal{A}}$. From hypotheses (28)(b) and (30)(b), we apply Hölder inequality directly to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|G(t_1, w_1, \mathbf{u}) - G(t_2, w_2, \mathbf{u})\|_{V^*} &= \sup_{\mathbf{v} \in V, \|\mathbf{v}\|_V=1} \langle G(t_1, w_1, \mathbf{u}) - G(t_2, w_2, \mathbf{u}), \mathbf{v} \rangle_V \\ & \leq L_{\mathcal{A}} |t_1 - t_2| + L_p m_0 \|w_1 - w_2\|_X \end{aligned}$$

for all $\mathbf{u} \in K$, where $m_0 > 0$ is such that $\|v_\nu\|_{L^2(\Gamma_3)} \leq m_0 \|\mathbf{v}\|_V$ for all $\mathbf{v} \in V$. Therefore, $H(G)$ (ii) is valid for $L_G := \max\{L_{\mathcal{A}}, L_p m_0\}$.

Let $J \subset I$ be any compact set, and $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2 \in C(I; V)$. Using (29) and Hölder inequality, it is not difficult to reveal

$$\|(\mathcal{R}\mathbf{z}_1)(t) - (\mathcal{R}\mathbf{z}_2)(t)\|_{V^*} \leq L'_J \int_0^t \|\mathbf{z}_1(s) - \mathbf{z}_2(s)\|_V ds$$

for all $t \in J$ for some $L'_J > 0$, namely, \mathcal{R} is a history-dependent operator.

From the formulation of φ , see (40), we can see that $\mathbf{v} \mapsto \varphi(w, \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ is linear and continuous. Additionally, a simple calculating gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi(w_1, \mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{v}_2) - \varphi(w_1, \mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{v}_1) + \varphi(w_2, \mathbf{v}_2^*, \mathbf{u}_2, \mathbf{v}_1) - \varphi(w_2, \mathbf{v}_2^*, \mathbf{u}_2, \mathbf{v}_2) \\ &= \int_{\Gamma_3} \eta(p(u_{\nu,1} - w_1) - p(u_{\nu,2} - w_2)) \mathbf{n}^*(t) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\tau,2} - \mathbf{v}_{\tau,1}) d\Gamma \\ & \quad + \langle \mathbf{v}_1^* - \mathbf{v}_2^*, \mathbf{v}_2 - \mathbf{v}_1 \rangle_V \\ & \leq \alpha_\varphi \|\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2\|_V \|\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2\|_V + \beta_\varphi \|\mathbf{v}_1^* - \mathbf{v}_2^*\|_{V^*} \|\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2\|_V \\ & \quad + \gamma_\varphi \|w_1 - w_2\|_X \|\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2\|_V \end{aligned}$$

for all $w_1, w_2 \in X$, $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2 \in V$ and all $\mathbf{v}_1^*, \mathbf{v}_2^* \in V^*$, where $\alpha_\varphi := L_p \|\eta\|_{L^\infty(\Gamma_3)}$ and for some $\beta_\varphi, \gamma_\varphi > 0$. Here, we have used hypotheses (30) and Hölder inequality.

Furthermore, it is obvious that the function $F: I \times X \times V \rightarrow X$ defined in (43) reads $H(F)$ (see assumptions (33)). For function j defined in (42), using inequality (45) and relaxed monotone condition (34)(d) implies

$$\begin{aligned} & j^0(\mathbf{u}; \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) + j^0(\mathbf{v}; \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) \\ & \leq \int_{\Gamma_4} j_\nu^0(\mathbf{x}, u_\nu(\mathbf{x}); v_\nu(\mathbf{x}) - u_\nu(\mathbf{x})) + j_\nu^0(\mathbf{x}, v_\nu(\mathbf{x}); u_\nu(\mathbf{x}) - v_\nu(\mathbf{x})) d\mathbf{x} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \alpha_{j_\nu} \int_{\Gamma_4} |u_\nu(\mathbf{x}) - v_\nu(\mathbf{x})|^2 d\Gamma \\ &\leq \alpha_{j_\nu} r_0^2 \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_V^2 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$. So, $H(j)$ (iii) holds for $\alpha_j = \alpha_{j_\nu} r_0^2$. Because of (34)(c) and (46), it is not difficult to verify that $H(j)$ (ii) is available for some $c_j > 0$.

We have verified all of conditions in Theorem 3.1, so, invoking this theorem concludes that problem (43)–(44) has a unique solution $(\mathbf{u}, w) \in C(I; K) \times C(I; L^2(\Gamma_3))$.

Finally, we will show that Problem 3 is unique solvability. Let $(\mathbf{u}_1, w_1), (\mathbf{u}_2, w_2) \in C(I; K) \times C(I; L^2(\Gamma_3))$ be two solutions to Problem 3. A simple calculating gives

$$\begin{aligned} &\|\mathbf{u}_1(t) - \mathbf{u}_2(t)\|_V \\ &\leq \frac{(L_G + \gamma_\varphi)}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \|w_1(t) - w_2(t)\|_X + \frac{\beta_\varphi L_J}{(m_G - \alpha_j - \alpha_\varphi)} \int_0^t \|\mathbf{u}_1(s) - \mathbf{u}_2(s)\|_V ds \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\|w_1(t) - w_2(t)\|_X \leq L_J e^{L_J t} \int_0^t \|\mathbf{u}_1(s) - \mathbf{u}_2(s)\|_V ds$$

for all $t \in J$ with some $L_J > 0$, where $J \subset I$ is compact. Combining the above inequalities and Gronwall's inequality, we conclude that $w_1 = w_2$ and $\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{u}_2$. Therefore, Problem 3 has a unique solution $(\mathbf{u}, w) \in C(I; K) \times C(I; L^2(\Gamma_3))$. \square

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